

DEVELOPING INTEREST IN READING TEXTS IN THE SPECIALTY AMONG STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. This article discusses some principles of work for creating interest in reading. It is noted that in order to develop an interest in reading, it is necessary to form among students a sustainable interest in learning foreign languages, where it is necessary to take into account the requirements of the future profession.

Keywords: learning to read, formation of sustainable interest, method, foreign language, cognitive need.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main goals in teaching a foreign language at a non-linguistic university is to develop students' skills in reading original literature in their specialty [4]. The ability to read is of great importance for the acquisition of all other speech skills.

To achieve this goal, first of all, it is necessary to form among students a sustainable interest in learning foreign languages, in particular, an interest in reading specialized literature [1]. This path, according to many scientists, is the most promising and effective in the educational practice of non-linguistic universities [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To create a student's interest in reading means to create a need to extract information, which corresponds to the goals of studying a foreign language in higher education. The task of the university at the first stage of education is to

develop interest in targeted reading, as an inexhaustible source of various knowledge.

When developing interest in reading among first-year students, it is necessary to be guided by the principles of practical orientation. Teaching a student a foreign language, in particular reading, will become effective if it meets the requirements of his future profession [4].

In order to implement this principle, it is recommended:

- familiarizing students with program requirements in a foreign language, while it must be indicated that untranslated reading of literature in the specialty is basic;
- familiarization with foreign journals, providing brief information about these sources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Of great importance for the formation of interest in a foreign language is the consistent implementation of the principle of accessibility. Teachers are well aware that in the first year students experience a gap between their actual knowledge, skills and the requirements of the university program. In order to bridge this gap, many scientists propose to gradually increase the difficulty of the texts being read. So, for example, in the first semester you can take textbook texts and newspaper material, and in the second semester you can use general scientific texts. The formation of interest in this literature is determined by a careful and skillful selection of texts from the point of view of their accessibility and the attitude that precedes direct work on them. So, for example, before reading a text in a specialty, it is necessary to show the significance of this text for the upcoming exam, indicating that it will help to better understand one of the sections of science. Or focus students' attention on the fact that the answers to the questions that follow the reading will indicate not only the understanding of this text, but also the knowledge acquired at school on this subject.

As the texts become more complex in the second semester, in order to further develop interest in reading, it is necessary to take a selective approach to the material being read.

To do this, you need to do the following exercises:

- 1) formulate the main idea of the sentence read briefly, to begin one or several paragraphs, and then the entire text;
- 2) name sentences and paragraphs of text that can be omitted;
- 3) name sentences and paragraphs of text that contain basic information;
- 4) the teacher read or write several sentences on the board, only one of which reflects the main idea of the text;
- 5) offer to quickly name sentences that carry the main content; which can be omitted; form the essence of a text in a foreign language.

It is worth noting here that competition in the classroom creates an atmosphere of interest and significantly speeds up the process of extracting information [3]. The ability to quickly navigate the logical structure of a text allows you to minimize the time spent consulting a dictionary and deepens your understanding of the text and interest in reading.

A few words about the principle of novelty, which is the most significant in the formation of interest. This principle is based on cognitive need. However, this need can act as a stimulator of interest only if, as a result of reading, it finds appropriate material to satisfy it. It follows that work with first-year students must begin with reading texts that provide educational value, and not repeat school topics. As for topics for the development of oral speech skills, which also contribute to the formation of interest in reading, it makes sense to replace traditional university topics with texts related to the life of your university, city, native language, etc.

To develop an interest in reading, it is necessary to gradually develop speed reading skills. This work must be carried out from the second semester. Since we

are talking about the initial stage of learning, the main attention is paid to learning reading. For this purpose, you can offer students the following tasks.

1. Offer a text with one question. After the time has elapsed, check the correctness of the answer.

2. Read the text aloud with the intention of understanding the questions proposed in advance.

3. Offer students a written translation of the text with subsequent recording of the time spent by each student on the translation.

CONCLUSION

In order to develop interest in reading, it is necessary to note the importance of dialogic conversation as a form of control over what is read. These conversations can be diversified by practicing the methodology for conducting them and thereby increasing the effectiveness. When working on a newspaper text, you can choose a “political observer” from among the strong students, and all the other students ask questions about the text they read. This form of work creates an emotional upsurge, brings revitalization, which is a necessary condition for the development of interest, and therefore for learning a foreign language in general.

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